

Integrating electromagnetics and signal processing into new radar algorithms

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Abstract – Modern remote sensing applications, including radar, require thoughtful consideration of electromagnetic principles for constructing advanced signal processing algorithms for detection, estimation, tracking, imaging and feature extraction. Starting from a generalized picture of the distributed sensing paradigm, this paper presents current efforts at the Radar Instrumentation Laboratory, Air Force Institute of Technology to develop efficient target models for use in integrated imaging and feature extraction algorithms for fully polarimetric synthetic aperture radar (SAR). In continuing the development of anisotropic target models, closed form expressions are presented for canonical objects, and using both simulation and measurement from the Gotcha challenge data, a new and efficient integrated algorithm is demonstrated for finding distributed objects in SAR imagery.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, the Air Force Institute of Technology has integrated a hands-on radar instrumentation laboratory and a computational electromagnetics (EM) laboratory with a well-established radar signal processing (RSP) program to form a comprehensive radar curriculum [1-5]. Today, students and faculty conduct intra-disciplinary research that demonstrates the importance of combined signal processing and EM physics with particular emphasis on radar imaging.

It is the experience of the authors that many works in distributed sensing begin with either a set of complex numbers and associated statistical distributions or from Maxwell's equations and integro-differential operators. From a teaching perspective, these approaches are useful for focusing on a single or small skill set. However, for solving practical radar-based problems, it is clear from the increasing number of EM/RSP venues that a higher level perspective and immediate appreciation for all disciplines involved serve as a better starting point. This line of thinking has encouraged the development of a hands-on Radar Instrumentation Laboratory (RAIL) that combines high fidelity EM and RSP simulation with real measurement capability. In broadening the perspective of the radar curriculum, it

is a natural step to generalize the remote sensing paradigm to include different and multiple sensing technologies in a single system or common framework.

The generalization also provides greater insight into the symbiotic nature between the physics-based forward problem and algorithm-based inversion problem. It also highlights algorithms that are common across different sensor types. This paper presents an overview of the generalized remote sensing model and philosophy adopted by RAIL researchers and showcases recent works from not only the individual EM and RSP aspects, but also in new feature extraction algorithms for SAR imagery.

2 GENERALIZED REMOTE SENSING

Figure 1 shows the generalized model where a single sensing technology is easily seen to include a stimulus and sensor pair for a given environment (background land, sea, air, aircraft, vehicles, etcetera). Information is gleaned after data processing and interpretation by a human or machine. In the case of the classic air traffic control radar, the system includes a transmitter and receiver pair operating in a land-air environment followed by a matched filter and threshold detection processor. Of course moving target indication, clutter cancellation, and Doppler processing are assumed. The last stage of the generalized model is the display where a human or automated tracking algorithm observes detection history and surmises track behavior based on that history.

Now, in considering electro-optic (EO) or infrared (IR) sensing, the stimuli are different and the physical phenomena also differ, i.e., natural sunlight radiates into the environment and the EO sensor detects energy reflected from the environment, whereas the

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Fig. 1. The generalized remote sensing framework. Multiple and Different and multiple sensing technologies are included along with different individual or fusion algorithms. Information is derived by either automated systems, human systems or both and information is preserved for reuse.

IR detector senses EM radiation caused by blackbody radiation from objects in the environment. Yet, it is clear that when EO, IR and radar technologies are used together and in a distributed employment, there is individual image processing and tracking algorithms for each, fusing algorithms and even consideration of a priori or reuse of posteriori information. This starting point encompasses these aspects and also engenders appreciation of computer science and hardware implementation.

Although the inversion or algorithmic piece may appear to be independent of the physics, close inspection shows that the individual and mutual algorithms rely greatly on a deep understanding of the physical interaction of the stimulus energy with the environment and what can be observed by the sensor. This picture then requires a mathematical overlay representing physical and non-physical relationships between all of the blocks in a non-linear fashion. For example, most radar imaging algorithms immediately assume linearization of the forward scattering problem and far-field or plane-wave behavior so that the forward operator can be modeled with a simple Fourier operator. Hence, the algorithm needed to estimate the reflectivity or the radar cross section is an inverse Fourier operator. Of course, the receiver is represented as a windowing operation that restricts the support of the Fourier operator. In near-field applications such as sub-surface sensing, the linearized EM model may not provide sufficiently accurate representation causing the detection and imaging quality to suffer. None-the-less, the model

reveals where assumptions lie and provides a means for discovering both analytically and empirically the effects of violating underlying assumptions. This is an active area of research for performance-based modeling. In the next section, new parametric models of EM scattering from 3D canonical objects is shown for use in SAR feature extraction algorithms.

3 MODELING OF SCATTERING PHYSICS

In creating a scattered field data set, the forward problem to model the sensed fields and signals-requires detailed models of the physical environment, which takes time and money in the form of labor and computational resources. Likewise, the inverse problem depends on high fidelity scattered field data and lots of it under many different scenarios. There exist multiple approaches categorized as nonparametric or parametric.

Nonparametric approaches attempt to locate scattering surfaces via solutions to the wave equation which are nearly always numerical in nature. These include probe methods such as the factorization method or linear sampling method. Parametric approaches use closed-form expressions that depend on scatterer attributes, such as location and size, and attempt to fit (in a least-squares sense) combinations of scatterer models to the observed radar signature. Parametric models include point scatterer models,

Fig. 2 Notional example of modeling a vehicle with scattering of varying complexity and comparison versus electromagnetic accuracy.

two dimensional (2D) attributed scatterers [3] and three-dimensional (3D) attributed scatterers [4]. Figure 2 shows a notional example of modeling a vehicle with the aforementioned parametric scattering models and numerical methods. A qualitative comparison of model complexity versus accuracy is also shown. An ideal scattering model will have low computational complexity, high electromagnetic accuracy, and be mathematically invertible.

Analytic derivation of geometric optics (GO), physical optics, diffraction theory (GTD), etc. may be computed for scattering primitives to replace numerical methods for obtaining accurate scattering models. An example of such a model is derived in [5] for bistatic scattering in three-dimensions from a right-angle dihedral. The resulting model equation is lengthy but computationally efficient and accurate within certain frequency limits of the underlying GO/GTD. The equation may be simplified to achieve a model that is easily inverted— that is, a model where the dihedral parameters are easily estimated from observed radar data.

High-frequency radar scattering analysis often assumes an isotropic point scatterer model. Point model scattering is simply a complex sinusoid with additive random noise and facilitates use of standard spectral estimation methods such as CLEAN [6]; FFT, Capon, MUSIC [7]; and other sidelobe and speckle reduction methods. However, the point model does not account for scattering behavior as a function of aspect angle or polarization, important elements of target signature characterization.

Aspect-dependent, attributed scattering center models proposed in [8] provide a single representation that applies to both localized and distributed scattering centers in 2D SAR images. Although the 2D attributed models do fit to the scattered energy in the image, they do not capture the real-world 3D scattering physics. Scattering primitives in 3D were proposed [4] for the general 3D bistatic scattering scenario (of which monostatic and 2D scattering are special cases). The primitives considered were the plate, dihedral, trihedral, cylinder, top-hat, and sphere. These 3D primitives more accurately describe the aspect dependent scattering from real-world scattering geometry. The 3D primitive models are specified by individual model equations for each shape and include parameterizations for radar frequency, polarization, and aspect angles, and target location, pose, and size. The next section illustrates the use of the parametric model in feature extraction algorithms including a new integrated imaging-classification algorithm.

4 IMAGING-EXTRACTION ALGORITHM

Although the 3D primitives more accurately capture the scattering physics, the task of target signature characterization is complicated by the introduction of multiple signal models and a large number of parameters. The characterization problem requires model order selection (to determine the number of scattering mechanisms present), signature classification (to assign a particular primitive), and parameter estimation (to assign physical attributes to the mechanism). Furthermore, the classification and estimation problems are coupled. Following the approach in [9], Figure 3 depicts imaging and classification results of a canonical-object scene, where the primitive objects serve as a basis for describing complex distributed objects

In addition, challenges in using sparse data and nonlinear SAR apertures for 3D imagery and feature classification remain areas of active research. Here, efficient methods that capitalize on the parametric models are investigated for simultaneous imaging and classification of canonical objects. Recently, polarimetric-based algorithms were shown to enable automatic feature extraction during image formation. Using a domain-decomposition approach for fast backprojection imaging, time-frequency and least-squares classification algorithms were incorporated into a new algorithm that performs classification on a pulse-by-pulse basis. This approach enables one to arrive at the classification answer upon report of the image. This clear time savings is accomplished by the joint EM/RSP understanding.

Fig. 3 Classification and imaging of primitive objects. (a) Primitives: top hat, cylinder, dihedral, flat plate and sphere. (b) Simulated phase history in the Fourier Space. (c) Full aperture image. (d) Image and feature classification of Dodge Tacoma.

Lastly, the integrated algorithm was used with the Gotcha public release data set. Figure 4 shows results of the calibration targets (top hat and trihedral) which are in a weak clutter background. More recent are shown during the presentation.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This brief paper summarizes various works underway at the Radar Instrumentation Laboratory at the Air Force Institute of Technology.

Fig. 4. Example of the classification results using Gotcha data (pass 6, 2006 release).

Using a generalized model for remote sensing as a common framework for performance-based modeling of multiple and different sensor technologies, SAR feature extraction is used to demonstrate the inherent signal processing and electromagnetics. Details of the mathematical EM and RSP modeling will be presented during the accompanying talk.

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